

CXXC-type zinc finger protein 4 (CXXC4) : Time behavioural study of 3rd order combinations in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells

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Abstract

CXXC4 (or Dishevelled DVL-binding protein - inhibition of the DVL and AXIN complex (IDAX)) encodes a CXXC-type zinc finger domain-containing protein that antagonizes the canonical WNT signaling pathway. This domain contains eight conserved cysteine residues that bind to two zinc ions. The encoded protein negatively regulates WNT signaling through interaction with the postsynaptic density protein (PSD95) / Drosophila disc large tumor suppressor (DlgA) / zonula occludens-1 protein (ZO-1) or (PDZ) protein domain of DVL, that is required for the stabilization of the transcriptional co-activator β -catenin. Gujral and MacBeath [1] provides a quantitative, and dynamic study of WNT3A-mediated stimulation of HEK 293 cells, where they record time based expression profiles of several response genes which correlated significantly with proliferation and migration. By monitoring the dynamics of gene expression using self-organizing maps, they identified clusters of genes that exhibit similar expression dynamics and uncovered previously unrecognized positive and negative feedback loops. However, their study depicts/uses singular measurements of individual gene expression at different time snapshots/points to infer the system wide analysis of the pathway. At any particular time point, it is often the case that genes are working synergistically in combinations, even though their expression measurements are singular in nature. Here, I • enumerate and rank all 2415 CXXC4 related 3rd order combinations in a forest of ${}^{71}C_3$ combinations using four different sensitivity methods; • show the conserved rankings for CXXC4-X-X combinations, which point to existence of biological synergy of some of these combinations across the different sensitivity methods; and • study the behaviour of some of these combinations related to WNT3A response genes that are ranked by the machine learning search engine (Sinha [2]) in time. Patterns of combinations emerge, some of which have been tested in wet lab, while others require further wet lab analysis.

[☆]Time behavioural study of 3-odr CXXC4 comb. in WNT3A stimulated cells

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1. Significance

Sinha [2] recently demonstrated the use of machine learning based search engine to rank/reveal gene combinations at 2nd order for the time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1] and showed how it is possible to locate combinations of priority that might be working synergistically, using sensitivity methods and powerful support vector ranking algorithm. However, the problem explodes combinatorially with even a small set of 71 recorded genes in the study by Gujral and MacBeath [1], when one steps to explore 3rd order combinations. With the total number of ${}^{71}C_3$ (= 57155) combinations, it becomes nearly impossible for any biologist to study the system wide dynamics of any pathway. Also, the amount of time usually needed to search for and test a combination is far more than the search down by the machine learning based search engine. Here, I extend the research work by Sinha [2] to conduct a behavioral study of 3rd order CXXC4 related combinations using individual gene expressions measured in time, in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells.

2. Introduction

The details of the machine learning based search engine has been recently published in Sinha [2] and deployed to explore the 2nd order combinations of genes in the data set provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. Nevertheless, here, I point to the fundamentals of the published work for completeness.

2.1. A combinatorial problem

Sensitivity analysis plays a major role in computing the strength of the influence of involved factors in any phenomena under investigation. When applied to expression profiles of various intra/extracellular factors that form an integral part of a signaling pathway, the variance and density based analysis yields a range of sensitivity indices for individual as well as various combinations of factors. These combinations denote the higher order interactions among the involved factors. Computation of higher order interactions is often time consuming but it gives a chance to explore the various combinations that might be of interest in the working mechanism of the pathway. For example, in a range of fourth order combinations among the various factors of the Wnt pathway, it would be easy to assess the influence of the destruction complex formed by APC, AXIN, CSKI and GSK3 interaction. But the effect of these combinations vary over time as measurements of fold changes and deviations in fold changes vary. So it is imperative to know how an interaction or a combination of the involved factors behave in time and Sinha [2] develops a procedure to track the behaviour by exploiting the influences of these involved factors.

2.2. A possible solution

In this work, after estimating the individual effects of factors for a higher order combination, the individual indices are considered as discriminative features. A combination, then, is a feature set in higher order (≥ 2 , i.e. multivariate). With an excessively large number of factors involved in the pathway, it is difficult to search for important combinations in a wide search space over different orders. Exploiting the analogy with the issues of prioritizing webpages using ranking algorithms, for a particular order, a full set of combinations of interactions can then be prioritized based on these features using a powerful ranking algorithm via support vectors Joachims [3]. Recording the changing rankings of the combinations over time reveals how higher order interactions behave within the pathway and when an intervention might be necessary to influence the interaction within the pathway.

2.3. CXXC-type zinc finger protein 4 (CXXC4)

CXXC4 is belongs to the class of Zinc fingers. A zinc finger is a small protein structural motif which contain multiple finger-like protrusions that make contacts with their target molecule and are characterized by the coordination of one or more zinc ions (Zn^{2+}) which stabilizes the fold. Some of these domains bind zinc, but many do not; instead binding other metals such as iron, or no metal at all. This domain contains eight conserved cysteine residues that bind to two zinc ions. The CXXC domain is found in a variety of chromatin-associated proteins and binds to non-methylated CpG dinucleotides. The domain is characterised by two CGXCXXC repeats.

In attempting to clarify the roles of DVL in the WNT signaling pathway, Hino et al. [4] identified a novel protein which binds to the PDZ domain of DVL and named it IDAX (for inhibition of the Dvl and Axin complex or CXXC4). IDAX and AXIN competed with each other for the binding to DVL and immunocytochemical analyses showed that the former was localized to the same place as DVL in cells and that expression of the later inhibited the colocalization of DVL and IDAX. Further, WNT-induced accumulation of β -catenin and activation of T-cell factor in mammalian cells were suppressed by expression of Idax. Since DVL is a positive regulator in the WNT signaling pathway and that the PDZ domain is important for this activity, their results suggested that IDAX acted as a negative regulator of the WNT signaling pathway by directly binding to the PDZ domain of Dvl.

Kojima et al. [5] identified a CXXC4 homozygous deletion at 4q24 in an aggressive renal cell carcinoma (RCC) using single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) arrays. They found significantly lower CXXC4 mRNA levels in tumor samples in patients with metastases compared with those without. Further, knockdown of CXXC4 induced the nuclear translocation of β -catenin and altered expression of a set of genes involved in cell proliferation, invasion and survival.

I present 3rd order combinations of CXXC4 with other genes, that the machine learning based search engine points to, as possible synergistic combinations that might be working in time.

3. Methods

Please refer to sections of Sinha [2] for methods, design of study and analysis of data for 2nd order combinations. The same method and design of study is used to generate results for 3rd order combinations presented in this study.

4. Time series data

Gujral and MacBeath [1] present a set of 71 WNT-related gene expression values for 6 different times points over a range of 24-hour period using qPCR. The changes represent the fold-change in the expression levels of genes in 200 ng/mL WNT3A-stimulated HEK 293 cells in time relative to their levels in unstimulated, serum-starved cells at 0-hour. Gujral and MacBeath [1] state that qPCR data are the means of three biological replicates. Only genes whose mean transcript levels changed by more than two-fold at one or more time points during the 24-hour time course were considered significant. Positive (negative) numbers represent up (down) -regulation. We have already covered the issues related to these data sets in detail in Sinha [6]. Readers are requested to go through them in the pointed reference. The tools of study which are used here have been published in another foundational work in Sinha [6].

5. Design of experiment

5.1. Pipeline for time series data

For the case of time series data, interactions among the contributing factors are studied by comparing triplets of fold-changes at single time points. The procedure begins with the generation of distribution around measurements at single time points with added noise is done to estimate the indices. A distribution is generated for the fold changes at single time points. Then for every gene, there is a vector of values representing fold changes as well as deviations in fold changes for different time points and durations between time points, respectively. Next a listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes is generated. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represents a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. After this, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in the required format from the distributions for two separate cases which have been discussed above. (See .R code in mainScript-1-1.R). After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations. This procedure is done for different kinds of sensitivity analysis methods.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Since there is only one

recording of sensitivity index per combination, each combination forms a training example which is allotted a training index and the sensitivity indices of the individual genetic factors form the training example. Thus there are C_k^n training examples for k^{th} order interaction. Using this training set SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [3] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [3]. Note that due to availability of only one example per combination, after the model has been built, the same training data is used as test data to generate the scores. This procedure is executed for each and every sensitivity analysis method. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices (i.e the training indices) already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm. Finally, this entire procedure is computed for sensitivity indices generated for each and every fold change at time point and deviations in fold change at different durations. Observing the changing rank of a particular combination at different times and different time periods will reveal how a combination is behaving.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R, in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("mainScript-1-1.R") with arguments for Dynamic data • source("SVMRank-Results-D.R"), to rank the interactions (again this needs to be done separately for different kinds of SA methods), • use source("Combine-Time-files.R"), if computing indices separately via previous file, • source("Sort-n-Plot-D.R") to sort the interactions. Note that the sorting is changes the interaction ranking in time. Thus • use source("Interaction-Priority-Intime.R") to find the prioritized ranking of each and every interaction over the different time points and finally • use source("Print-Ranking-AND-Interaction-Rank.R") to print individual ranking of the required input factor with other interaction factors.

6. Results & Discussion

6.1. Time series data by Gujral and MacBeath [1]

NOTE - Ranking was assigned on scores that were sorted in DECREASING values. So, 1 was assigned to highest score and vice versa.

Results for the 3rd order interactions are presented here. The results first discuss the behaviour of interactions across the snapshots of time using the computed sensitivities on fold change measurements per time snapshot. The analysis was done using 4 different sensitivity indices. Out of the 7_1C_3 combinations, I consider/present only those combinations that show a ranking within first 10,000 out of 57,155. This choice is liberal and biologists/oncologists can have a more stricter choice as per need. Two observations are made, • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved (i.e within the 10,000 range) in a particular time point or in the early phase or late phase of WNT3A stimulation, across the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is a

strict criteria of assessment or • the ranking of a particular combination is conserved across time points/phase (i.e they are within the 10,000 range) and the majority of the four sensitivity methods, which is relaxed criteria of assessment. Applying this filter helps reveal important combinations of interest that might be working synergistically at a higher order level in the cell.

Regarding technical points of implementation, the rankings were generated without scaling/normalizing the time series data provided by Gujral and MacBeath [1]. For estimating the sensitivity indices, a small gaussian distribution using the function **rnorm** that generates a vector of normally distributed random variables given a vector length n (here 9, the 10th one is the mean/recorded gene regulation itself), a population mean μ and population standard deviation σ . The syntax for using **rnorm** is as follows: **rnorm(n, mean, sd)**. Further, I use the **jitter** function to add a little bit of noise to the data. This helps to see if the generated rankings are robust or not.

6.2. Enumeration and ranking of 2415 CXXC4-X-X combinations from Gujral and MacBeath [1]

In the supplementary section, I present four files, each containing the rankings of 3rd order combinations, that vary in time (shown for 5 time points). Each file represents the rankings computed using a particular sensitivity method. The changing rankings in time for a particular combination represents the importance of contribution/role that combination plays in the cell stimulated with WNT3A. The sensitivity methods used are Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion indices (HSIC) indices (with rbf and linear kernel in Da Veiga [7]) and Sobol indices (with 2002 implementation in Saltelli [8] and martinez implementation in Martinez [9] and Baudin et al. [10]).

6.3. Conserved machine learning rankings for tested CXXC4-X-X combinations

A total of 2415, 3rd order combinations involving CXXC4 were obtained from a full set of ${}^71C_3 = 57155$ combinations. Further, from this selected set, using the above criteria for conserved rankings, I report/tabulate the meaningful combinations that might be working synergistically. Tables 2, 3 and 4 show the rankings for the same combinations as in table 1, but using rbf kernel for HSIC, 2002 implementation for SOBOL and martinez implementation for SOBOL, respectively. As one tallies the rankings of across these tables for a particular combination, one finds that the role of the combination of interest is conserved. This conservation points to the existence of the biological synergy, whether the combination has been tested or unexplored/untested.

6.3.1. Examining the behaviour of DVL-CXXC4-X combinations

It is known from above literature that CXXC4 binds with DVL to antagonize the WNT signaling pathway. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of DVL family along with CXXC4, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CXXC4-DVL2-FRZB, CXXC4-DVL2-SFRP4, CXXC4-DVL2-LRP5, CXXC4-DVL2-RHO, CXXC4-DVL2-WNT2B, CXXC4-DVL2-FZD1 and CXXC4-DVL2-WNT3A.

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - LINEAR

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CXXC4-PORCN-SENP2	10	33446	17033	17387	32253	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT4	49	6186	19448	20672	51388
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT2B	60	17097	46765	26682	32940	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	64	19925	35266	282	20625
CXXC4-PORCN-SFRP4	80	28448	27819	28835	44315	CXXC4-FOSL1-SENP2	88	36639	18548	29008	12844
CXXC4-FZD7-PPP2CA	90	9819	23105	12397	36836	CXXC4-FZD7-SFRP4	136	18277	38915	34583	33873
CXXC4-PORCN-TCF7	147	56042	37081	25343	32394	CXXC4-PORCN-FBXW4	168	26465	19028	12201	29004
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	212	18126	46011	57	25507	CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	255	24314	35136	31526	39110
CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	296	10717	21805	2575	15715	CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	304	26037	23203	450	10918
CXXC4-FGF4-SENP2	325	44612	33138	54156	47148	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2R1A	424	27798	37533	50501	37618
CXXC4-FGF4-FRZB	461	19762	30000	22761	54575	CXXC4-FZD7-WNT2B	472	12278	44001	31202	33433
CXXC4-DVL2-FRZB	479	9516	3524	8282	38815	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2CA	481	22027	38709	38555	36190
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	491	167	4767	2069	15953	CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	519	13366	30568	2083	18784
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT5A	535	15961	16253	55679	46631	CXXC4-FGF4-RHOU	583	24551	34633	53319	56248
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	591	19400	24702	2318	5774	CXXC4-DVL2-RHOU	703	7173	6556	19343	52966
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	731	20058	29538	14504	27891	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	764	1040	837	11709	30876
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP5	826	10603	47963	24020	51425	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	827	10881	39520	3401	24688
CXXC4-JUN-SENP2	843	21048	50347	6595	9660	CXXC4-FGF4-TLE2	870	21534	50726	38272	53250
CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	881	1789	43156	41625	53423	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3A	905	28520	52397	52668	30693
CXXC4-PGF4-WNT5A	957	4552	41511	51712	55041	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	971	1353	33173	6860	26690
CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2R1A	1044	30931	36251	44472	52608	CXXC4-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	1089	2458	1605	6818	34700
CXXC4-FGF4-TCF7	1091	38819	31734	49434	48726	CXNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	1094	46700	26853	25310	54546
CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	1138	13192	17971	6537	17461	CXXC4-FOXN1-RHOU	1258	949	4951	19719	52102
CXNK1D-CXXC4-FZD1	1263	2919	24873	24770	29960	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	1308	4014	25558	7639	24982
CXXC4-DVL2-SFRP4	1347	5287	2872	6219	37139	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT2B	1361	15018	7269	31481	39016
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	1368	22243	14796	45725	54959	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	1379	21025	34076	34379	37036
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	1421	24998	29856	17406	1342	CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	1467	3249	13379	2815	22591
CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	1496	10929	38139	43065	17470	CXXC4-FOXN1-FRZB	1502	99	9554	17642	46105
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	1520	3860	3645	1038	15312	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	1561	16594	47993	27451	26786
CXXC4-FZD2-LEF1	1642	3090	9287	23149	51524	CXXC4-GSK3A-WNT2	1689	13832	6873	29230	43303
CXXC4-WIF1-WNT3A	1745	353	12465	51440	34488	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT4	1747	5857	34419	49599	54246
CXXC4-GSK4-FZD1	1751	11265	20257	55084	52255	CXXC4-FOXN1-SENP2	1771	9020	6263	7094	11868
CXXC4-FZD7-RHOU	1774	20795	27044	52150	54907	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2R1A	1782	11540	37923	13434	43762
CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	1800	15338	42242	52718	32578	CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	1810	3252	48463	383	12590
CXXC4-JUN-SLC9A3R1	1862	8225	23228	21414	44419	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	1948	42829	14565	52294	56300
CXXC4-FZD2-SFRP4	1951	1938	36455	2988	50465	CXXC4-DVL2-FZD1	2007	11971	18762	3053	35259
CXXC4-FZD1-SENP2	2050	40723	10326	38271	17504	CXXC4-FGF4-SFRP4	2200	21598	27619	50838	52265
CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	2202	5290	1484	56489	12898	CXXC4-NKD1-WNT2B	2217	9878	36698	23848	1631
CXXC4-GSK3A-RHOU	2262	20534	4082	47103	49826	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT3	2291	2240	24537	6255	30135
CXXC4-FZD2-RHOU	2317	6671	22273	26084	55079	CXXC4-FGF4-GSK3B	2336	2158	53607	41323	48886
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD8	2405	10212	3200	15737	15007	CXXC4-FOXN1-SFRP4	2487	1405	7515	14548	25337
CXNK1G1-CXXC4-DKK1	2488	45829	37872	27388	55403	CXNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	2496	24384	49297	7946	49881
CXXC4-FZD7-SENP2	2507	35237	27610	27855	26307	CXXC4-SFRP1-WNT2B	2551	24274	44184	31848	27946
BCL9-CXXC4-FZD7	2587	37095	21041	33971	29584	CXXC4-GSK3A-SFRP4	2604	10596	14291	21482	35934
CXXC4-FZD2-PPP2CA	2607	29974	9988	18663	50107	CXXC4-JUN-WNT4	2688	13375	46722	2824	3108
CXXC4-DVL2-LRP5	2699	16595	48005	8211	27106	CXXC4-WNT1-WNT3A	2734	34306	282	36977	4488
CXNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	2744	18327	34701	8594	2661	CXXC4-JUN-PITX2	2757	3424	36286	40345	36376
CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	2780	22054	41988	28791	40205	CXXC4-WIF1-WNT2	2794	318	38171	33660	55940
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT3A	2796	53	5860	22254	12575	CXXC4-GSK3A-LRP5	2801	2556	3529	23047	42324
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	2842	9594	30978	23790	51147	CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	2872	42910	42232	51357	48270
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	2894	23698	18152	32	32646	CXXC4-FZD2-SENP2	2916	26793	21261	5858	39928
CXXC4-FZD2-LRP5	2946	717	14065	26069	44141	CXXC4-FZD1-LRP5	2998	7300	42894	19351	29464
CXXC4-FZD2-GSK3B	3060	14042	29298	42224	44272	CXXC4-NKD1-SENP2	3069	14633	9774	13334	17352
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT5A	3109	8816	13105	18798	36097	CXXC4-NKD1-TLE2	3160	26	22413	13930	94
CXXC4-FOXN1-FBXW4	3181	4297	20629	11517	21464	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT3A	3186	7341	5733	24584	2313
CXNK1A1-CTBP2-CXXC4	3187	741	15084	41906	44957	CXXC4-GSK3A-SENP2	3196	30564	1921	32171	26223
CXXC4-FOXN1-PPP2CA	3277	19301	19575	24116	33763	CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2CA	3340	9402	29074	35299	53290
CXXC4-JUN-TLE1	3367	30489	24344	6356	85	CXXC4-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	3506	9586	9125	48353	50314
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT2	3532	201	7409	18120	37271	CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	3542	41044	29584	5685	51990
CXXC4-FZD1-FZD7	3585	25420	10832	32645	23514	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3	3619	587	35000	56680	49419
CXXC4-FOXN1-LRP5	3643	1872	9789	44781	31650	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2CA	3661	32213	26859	462	30021
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP6	3678	11467	49324	42483	34171	CXXC4-FZD7-TCF7	3714	44164	27210	52158	40111
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD6	3727	251	19904	12481	33219	CXXC4-FZD2-WNT2B	3800	9215	15294	40680	45553
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD8	3802	3981	51255	45882	40409	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	3843	4771	10375	1945	20127
CXXC4-FZD1-WNT4	3921	4043	24475	36885	25822	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	3932	2627	16679	25816	15722

Table 1: Rankings of CXXC4-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - linear

All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

RANKING @ t_i USING HSIC - RBF

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	9869	47028	41747	45009	41195	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT4	12492	2278	24920	46755	55842
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT2B	11272	21120	2288	41634	56160	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	4615	7359	56816	34657	49785
CXXC4-PORCN-SFRP4	9369	30775	45417	32220	54090	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	27232	42351	44650	16863	48178
CXXC4-FZD7-PPP2CA	7569	8146	8359	8809	29695	CXXC4-FZD7-SFRP4	20307	23535	39439	24195	53332
CXXC4-PORCN-TCF7	8174	50291	19771	4132	42869	CXXC4-PORCN-FBXW4	19853	43651	1014	10933	51164
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	38894	11877	48833	6512	54567	CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	52227	34156	6226	46113	43359
CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	7404	4364	36104	35047	22551	CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	14668	46919	1016	36914	42585
CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	252	42683	39239	31323	30294	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2R1A	20998	30567	5511	22186	56640
CXXC4-FGF4-FRZB	275	29756	38685	40122	49864	CXXC4-FZD7-WNT2B	3497	13030	1072	53710	54739
CXXC4-DVL2-FRZB	4886	7544	48054	28005	23326	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2CA	9663	20715	7491	12348	51537
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	22955	3089	37410	121	47163	CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	14983	16373	55100	8101	42887
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT5A	24704	5412	10695	26556	50085	CXXC4-FGF4-RHOU	2335	25378	25285	54463	41595
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	36361	6924	5576	32715	39457	CXXC4-DVL2-RHOU	24302	4880	47885	35622	25708
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	46607	15174	26086	25252	40912	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	2337	10507	41107	15818	46481
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP5	1846	12123	15671	39128	29876	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	6745	11128	54253	54080	39603
CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	1851	32478	55139	8858	43014	CXXC4-FGF4-TLE2	591	38121	27919	26190	19771
CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	7270	2533	37155	46380	45935	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3A	376	11041	597	49220	57138
CXXC4-FGF4-WNT5A	6438	9457	13415	42775	42269	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	15539	1611	30933	39991	28813
CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2R1A	1192	9614	5570	26405	23051	CXXC4-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	5835	4242	55138	22461	50612
CXXC4-FGF4-TCF7	1232	32544	24487	22245	56783	CXNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	18872	46435	17556	11771	54033
CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	14457	30498	1036	36322	33651	CXXC4-FOXN1-RHOU	4808	4398	51558	29746	40158
CXNK1D-CXXC4-FZD1	7144	1734	27303	7250	11481	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	8489	12877	51306	12233	26552
CXXC4-DVL2-SFRP4	16351	4938	49667	29954	34883	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT2B	14916	7821	10829	36605	32745
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	553	41867	29836	8057	53097	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	2896	16477	22826	15141	21339
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	5682	22392	33504	50525	42228	CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	21331	11904	46279	1885	30976
CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	15268	3842	31367	43633	53074	CXXC4-FOXN1-FRZB	2132	6567	49876	23824	32081
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	49331	4153	49861	27131	33193	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	5069	16399	50288	29076	25853
CXXC4-FZD2-LEF1	38950	1181	32681	4532	22634	CXXC4-GSK3A-WNT2	1230	15380	52831	13794	54110
CXXC4-WIF1-WNT3A	11746	12153	2343	56809	35373	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT4	299	4403	10799	6662	56255
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD1	412	10632	11544	31326	47937	CXXC4-FOXN1-SEN2	515	15255	52769	4140	43381
CXXC4-FZD7-RHOU	8290	22007	17701	54867	39963	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2R1A	8147	19410	4343	32567	48732
CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	53822	4385	5771	55698	30961	CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	23317	429	29024	48013	32482
CXXC4-JUN-SLC9A3R1	13688	4927	33829	15408	20050	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	1514	40573	41207	46205	49688
CXXC4-FZD2-SFRP4	16662	2511	31631	1790	20964	CXXC4-DVL2-FZD1	6039	15880	42432	32927	19633
CXXC4-FZD1-SEN2	34090	36346	54606	22792	22438	CXXC4-FGF4-SFRP4	1800	28754	47520	10479	30525
CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	28869	300	28004	21112	54426	CXXC4-NKD1-WNT2B	33112	30020	8852	27851	43373
CXXC4-GSK3A-RHOU	258	9516	53313	35938	49928	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT3	37775	8521	7319	54045	46168
CXXC4-FZD2-RHOU	10828	29932	33193	7959	25644	CXXC4-FGF4-GSK3B	2513	1585	2338	49143	54753
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD8	2538	22024	56449	30002	56254	CXXC4-FOXN1-SFRP4	2063	2782	54618	3345	15870
CXNK1G1-CXXC4-DKK1	18870	49739	2762	48160	29218	CXNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	10676	6045	28407	52045	39223
CXXC4-FZD7-SEN2	1262	39914	29126	38452	45236	CXXC4-SFRP1-WNT2B	9023	37294	3518	45010	56925
BCL9-CXXC4-FZD7	9941	29991	34446	25812	41178	CXXC4-GSK3A-SFRP4	170	13696	53514	4388	43098
CXXC4-FZD2-PPP2CA	11564	33338	12458	3001	54858	CXXC4-JUN-WNT4	4946	4363	31447	4600	32510
CXXC4-DVL2-LRP5	11745	7304	42550	26847	15371	CXXC4-WNT1-WNT3A	1236	41816	5972	30693	33822
CXNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	14134	8276	23947	22453	12908	CXXC4-JUN-PITX2	5093	2871	54929	54382	25342
CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	1507	4569	5986	44776	54536	CXXC4-WIF1-WNT2	51580	27076	41572	21992	55327
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT3A	2235	1906	54317	41438	43489	CXXC4-GSK3A-LRP5	385	9378	49161	34343	36785
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	4283	5655	31886	10011	47555	CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	3201	51583	32100	52166	52493
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	31513	32492	56401	22069	45177	CXXC4-FZD2-SEN2	11373	32779	36118	41772	48711
CXXC4-FZD2-LRP5	17864	7669	25949	15071	31594	CXXC4-FZD1-LRP5	50587	2520	47210	49401	49419
CXXC4-FZD2-GSK3B	11449	20532	5769	43469	53376	CXXC4-NKD1-SEN2	23566	21575	56539	18663	8724
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT5A	6575	17827	51655	52301	55304	CXXC4-NKD1-TLE2	14475	5894	51388	28114	51127
CXXC4-FOXN1-FBXW4	3459	16395	8588	13912	10169	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT3A	5548	8944	24906	33696	42805
CXNK1A1-CTBP2-CXXC4	6148	356	31122	45700	47540	CXXC4-GSK3A-SEN2	74	32451	54211	24002	33327
CXXC4-FOXN1-PPP2CA	1922	14941	49768	109	32177	CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2CA	896	24972	12137	33837	43059
CXXC4-JUN-TLE1	12052	20822	44884	32576	24749	CXXC4-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	467	8014	47156	13152	55436
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT2	4136	8477	52268	544	46007	CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	9306	45373	50696	51816	46911
CXXC4-FZD1-FZD7	49954	12547	56459	23869	41132	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3	3561	311	5182	29806	42876
CXXC4-FOXN1-LRP5	960	9617	46621	12430	9349	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2CA	2697	40480	12704	20114	45550
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP6	2697	40480	12704	20114	45550	CXXC4-FZD7-TCF7	7210	39983	16805	19991	41633
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD6	4475	608	35118	18286	44561	CXXC4-FZD2-WNT2B	20369	10806	14946	7965	25615
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD8	292	11900	36098	42761	36334	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	38206	4994	56442	3145	46853
CXXC4-FZD1-WNT4	34012	9183	32309	19082	29352	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	46697	2350	52931	39870	42513

Table 2: Rankings of CXXC4-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - HSIC; Kernel - rbf

6.3.2. Examining the behaviour of GSK3-CXXC4-X combinations

In gastric cancer, Lu et al. [11] show that CXXC4 interacts with DVL1 directly and the mutation of critical residues in the DVL-interacting domain abrogated its interac-

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - 2002

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	4981	10546	9375	17394	34482	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT4	9600	4879	1294	6463	37839
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT2B	39582	44080	51571	43634	12796	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	13855	16693	7772	24610	15521
CXXC4-PORCN-SFRP4	3428	54623	4989	9629	43028	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	9857	21302	3091	25681	49127
CXXC4-FZD7-PPP2CA	6148	28592	25213	26202	44025	CXXC4-FZD7-SFRP4	8226	37912	21420	24728	27141
CXXC4-PORCN-TCF7	2527	11671	4576	9976	25876	CXXC4-PORCN-FBXW4	53747	2497	52161	47571	14085
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	8172	787	10839	18520	17014	CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	33024	20784	45045	33319	8066
CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	9682	502	6322	25277	1837	CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	25898	41741	14499	23277	897
CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	56902	51611	35174	38140	4316	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2R1A	44156	3317	53822	38916	15985
CXXC4-FGF4-FRZB	655	16082	9480	20416	46553	CXXC4-FZD7-WNT2B	49726	31087	32815	31314	18255
CXXC4-DVL2-FRZB	6421	47272	15558	23096	47407	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2CA	13026	53831	3318	18245	41235
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	53246	51233	55370	49749	15337	CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	18548	15555	6549	27894	2409
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT5A	47497	52019	55859	50726	19154	CXXC4-FGF4-RHOU	252	5480	21939	19031	52845
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	5974	6674	24560	10110	44194	CXXC4-DVL2-RHOU	13662	45063	23761	15178	35600
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	13778	2749	16108	6403	43145	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	47401	2576	46879	53365	10616
CXXC4-DVL2-LRP5	19668	6338	18685	9517	51966	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	19654	576	4332	16136	19365
CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	8825	8401	12932	7871	27023	CXXC4-FGF4-TLE2	2464	6054	13953	11679	56111
CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	43332	26892	49071	46614	1986	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3A	7493	411	15315	24389	48926
CXXC4-FGF4-WNT5A	4008	46378	14592	16580	56090	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	33040	7608	43755	38567	13643
CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2R1A	6382	430	21801	13251	51268	CXXC4-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	3959	7438	19286	25956	7951
CXXC4-NLK-FRFP1	45370	46737	48467	45014	23299	CXNKIG1-CXXC4-FOSL1	25168	1437	11571	16056	25721
CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	49484	2831	37278	49282	3845	CXXC4-FOXN1-RHOU	49343	54575	54627	33981	50794
CXNK1D-CXXC4-FZD1	15838	20986	27843	15827	35450	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	7686	54368	19771	7870	53296
CXXC4-DVL2-SFRP4	40484	4674	42806	42655	30934	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT2B	6744	50339	17055	22295	46522
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	52810	50470	34544	37927	3516	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	1115	20606	6634	9559	44618
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	7869	2751	20454	26029	9961	CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	9628	4363	7425	17260	48958
CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	13879	27252	8058	10543	55180	CXXC4-FOXN1-FRZB	47727	56222	50026	44836	51771
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	17728	56469	8386	24896	33148	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	56040	37157	50497	47616	12624
CXXC4-DVL2-LEF1	43791	16576	35344	56737	19650	CXXC4-GSK3A-WNT2	55861	49041	34404	46788	7541
CXXC4-WIF1-WNT3A	54553	44801	48557	52030	1570	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT4	49638	56741	41820	32756	8361
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD1	10610	51496	17191	13677	52657	CXXC4-FOXN1-SEN2	20619	376	16314	23024	6715
CXXC4-FZD7-RHOU	42809	25100	32087	29550	5695	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2R1A	44274	1712	51774	45829	14514
CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	45823	54747	52368	41434	48001	CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	14447	55550	4187	25428	10791
CXXC4-JUN-SLC9A3R1	3663	5023	4043	7111	47297	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	9212	1819	7168	7601	47095
CXXC4-FZD2-SFRP4	50903	14206	47616	54449	8766	CXXC4-DVL2-FZD1	8469	13264	13510	23889	17063
CXXC4-FZD1-SEN2	12809	49359	6206	3069	42315	CXXC4-FGF4-SFRP4	44465	38386	38344	41294	134
CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	17363	10111	1772	5324	38194	CXXC4-NKD1-WNT2B	15436	10525	10086	1323	45129
CXXC4-GSK3A-RHOU	14260	7037	2619	8274	28887	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT3	13	8251	9046	18094	39176
CXXC4-FZD2-RHOU	6780	8109	9925	14270	49006	CXXC4-FGF4-GSK3B	9304	6529	4812	8493	41990
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD8	55264	46656	51687	38480	50201	CXXC4-FOXN1-SFRP4	13446	237	16807	20244	1750
CXNKIG1-CXXC4-DKK1	29722	16090	47827	56588	1654	CXNKIG1-CXXC4-FRAT1	27618	3778	3433	676	48257
CXXC4-FZD7-SEN2	4691	36054	25571	25112	38500	CXXC4-SFRP1-WNT2B	5270	10347	14597	16518	33006
BCL9-CXXC4-FZD7	12890	55435	14964	14600	32799	CXXC4-GSK3A-SFRP4	42048	44931	50649	47022	11196
CXXC4-FZD2-PPP2CA	48257	39680	46070	54823	47811	CXXC4-JUN-WNT4	11461	1911	4636	18755	45271
CXXC4-DVL2-LRP5	12022	50320	14484	24733	24341	CXXC4-WNT1-WNT3A	46602	51045	38468	51607	4562
CXNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	34042	35885	29812	41264	26139	CXXC4-JUN-PITX2	7081	3972	8713	3640	32183
CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	18745	698	6566	18659	49649	CXXC4-WIF1-WNT2	15365	18609	6335	8974	52925
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT3A	51263	50390	30984	42574	46666	CXXC4-GSK3A-LRP5	2369	28526	3451	15002	30988
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	50820	53673	45701	44615	8451	CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	38479	27988	31220	33378	4766
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	41126	2126	46459	30168	34144	CXXC4-FZD2-SEN2	50382	48962	47212	42891	8509
CXXC4-FZD2-LRP5	10970	45825	5695	222	27035	CXXC4-FZD1-LRP5	51552	42608	31364	30529	12998
CXXC4-FZD2-GSK3B	7116	23758	13803	1131	52308	CXXC4-NKD1-SEN2	53247	30638	52373	44913	3619
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT5A	45779	49880	48086	39298	56659	CXXC4-NKD1-TLE2	667	11124	4405	10259	37949
CXXC4-FOXN1-FBXW4	43717	56917	40334	36937	55377	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT3A	17336	51748	14847	23229	36228
CXNK1A1-CTBP2-CXXC4	32731	6104	30912	45061	27995	CXXC4-GSK3A-SEN2	42993	50176	54509	48854	28496
CXXC4-FOXN1-PPP2CA	3477	1511	1989	21870	13869	CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2CA	45268	56658	41145	41538	2318
CXXC4-JUN-TLE1	9806	54580	10229	3795	46539	CXXC4-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	55602	51900	49035	38962	23048
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT2	20914	24314	16648	24201	21980	CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	17526	25193	23946	23550	12450
CXXC4-FZD1-FZD7	11040	53941	8320	18995	41701	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3	37990	37288	42279	35654	7889
CXXC4-FOXN1-LRP5	42375	52933	50994	41421	52542	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2CA	12942	55409	5351	11313	42743
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP6	37441	50826	38434	47652	5185	CXXC4-FZD7-TCF7	7168	23159	23535	24415	44261
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD6	50432	53386	52863	37651	44074	CXXC4-FZD2-WNT2B	9145	29828	19209	12741	40862
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD8	2927	5577	12374	5513	30264	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	20204	45005	6311	11503	39338
CXXC4-FZD1-WNT4	18374	14688	10406	5900	46576	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	12448	41748	17765	12599	37639

Table 3: Rankings of CXXC4-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - 2002

tion with DVL1. Importantly, the association of DVL1 with AXIN1 and GSK3 β was disrupted upon the expression of wild-type but not the mutated CXXC4 that failed to interact with DVL1. Further, the wild-type but not the mutated CXXC4 reduced the amount of β -catenin and inhibited the phosphorylation of GSK3 β , while knockdown

RANKING @ t_i USING SOBOL - MARTINEZ

3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}	3rd order comb.	t_1	t_3	t_6	t_{12}	t_{24}
CXXC4-PORCN-SEN2	17800	21889	46576	9816	38838	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT4	4276	14596	42774	57022	45130
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT2B	14191	46734	705	50002	13918	CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	4524	34402	46794	6498	8094
CXXC4-PORCN-SFRP4	36656	48495	25105	56369	1896	CXXC4-FOSL1-SEN2	7660	26757	51210	21967	12513
CXXC4-FZD7-PPP2CA	36776	55789	52424	25177	54487	CXXC4-FZD7-SFRP4	8932	21246	56689	41181	37264
CXXC4-PORCN-TCF7	48699	31354	37070	38630	54197	CXXC4-PORCN-FBXW4	56939	49267	33951	53901	13207
CXXC4-FRAT1-TLE2	11724	43395	50755	17676	10023	CXXC4-FOSL1-PPP2R1A	12098	31961	43639	23246	42209
CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1	22778	53793	47414	21406	16409	CXXC4-FRAT1-FBXW4	987	15768	29512	11340	7983
CXXC4-FGF4-SEN2	56684	55582	53323	1516	51115	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2R1A	56184	21259	15139	35428	46765
CXXC4-FGF4-FRZB	8950	3819	46444	30145	14860	CXXC4-FZD7-WNT2B	47761	31077	51924	46061	8191
CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	33111	15756	56444	56623	51828	CXXC4-PORCN-PPP2CA	18980	12646	41076	17858	34882
CXXC4-NLK-WNT4	55944	14516	7372	46062	23888	CXXC4-FRAT1-TCF7L1	10737	32616	38921	7498	6441
CXXC4-PORCN-WNT5A	30469	36642	4574	55370	14476	CXXC4-FGF4-RHOU	38864	34297	38133	42615	15453
CXXC4-NLK-FBXW4	20852	11273	14078	12143	34383	CXXC4-DVL2-RHOU	28497	27073	51383	56020	325
CXXC4-FOSL1-FRAT1	9338	19582	40214	46514	45765	CXXC4-JUN-TLE2	54851	48414	34147	40148	9323
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP5	21307	32278	49771	53389	8336	CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8	4301	44390	15228	41861	45793
CXXC4-JUN-SEN2	45684	29715	54947	14159	18626	CXXC4-FGF4-TLE2	17448	46854	12084	50641	5048
CXXC4-JUN-RHOU	56140	21552	3493	38523	19065	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3A	10179	2559	53194	27467	11706
CXXC4-FGF4-WNT5A	14261	23219	50216	56128	9682	CXXC4-JUN-LRP5	14950	38582	26056	22260	14906
CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2R1A	8907	21944	29567	29533	9336	CXXC4-FOXN1-SLC9A3R1	45159	54481	6054	51467	4749
CXXC4-FRAT1-FRZB	48038	22643	53740	1196	41016	CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FOSL1	3540	41011	53892	1277	30939
CXXC4-JUN-FBXW4	54886	34793	20190	5710	9414	CXXC4-FOXN1-RHOU	50127	17786	8880	44528	47077
CSNK1D-CXXC4-FZD1	28112	48535	48166	35007	4846	CXXC4-JUN-SFRP4	13812	15293	47877	3185	27486
CXXC4-DVL2-SFRP4	44858	27481	43970	53001	32555	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT2B	35400	16086	45800	56946	44441
CXXC4-FGF4-FOSL1	56003	23413	39066	3360	54945	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7	11066	2375	24218	5640	51093
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A	36507	46562	51863	10238	16814	CXXC4-NLK-TLE2	13188	19135	45004	13965	42668
CXXC4-JUN-PYGO1	19004	24107	54656	40210	53966	CXXC4-FOXN1-FRZB	47960	19432	1581	42150	17714
CXXC4-NLK-SFRP1	39174	27767	26220	7903	4356	CXXC4-JUN-TCF7L1	55451	45389	163	3252	9752
CXXC4-FZD2-LEF1	38701	52570	29566	1484	9660	CXXC4-GSK3A-WNT2	31812	53767	32	18017	20951
CXXC4-WIF1-WNT3A	52245	44345	37185	10089	25395	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT4	53473	50248	53015	47741	53510
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD1	36967	31610	28448	56470	5199	CXXC4-FOXN1-SEN2	26092	39980	53378	7666	4514
CXXC4-FZD7-RHOU	35284	52733	39030	45511	8959	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2R1A	51605	35237	2	12177	38141
CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A	44523	32024	5826	41353	32438	CXXC4-FRAT1-LRP5	26342	36309	49368	17193	12600
CXXC4-JUN-SLC9A3R1	14356	55979	11051	16069	54131	CXXC4-FGF4-KREMEN1	9910	50112	48782	5621	8051
CXXC4-FZD2-SFRP4	54359	23575	3752	30270	34287	CXXC4-DVL2-FZD1	40155	13700	47483	55239	50111
CXXC4-FZD1-SEN2	10968	51534	28697	46936	999	CXXC4-FGF4-SFRP4	40604	55204	50918	25336	40518
CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B	7556	34332	12045	46119	55583	CXXC4-NKD1-WNT2B	42290	20950	47826	15060	49390
CXXC4-GSK3A-RHOU	30621	42466	3462	4635	54854	CXXC4-PORCN-WNT3	49304	25501	32130	16898	50343
CXXC4-FZD2-RHOU	14268	2526	46609	14987	7396	CXXC4-FGF4-GSK3B	2459	11975	38438	52895	15019
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD8	51827	31923	3200	25454	25723	CXXC4-FOXN1-SFRP4	32485	30641	19452	14615	1724
CSNK1G1-CXXC4-DKK1	21335	46326	26057	31544	22681	CSNK1G1-CXXC4-FRAT1	2838	20322	35155	3949	37439
CXXC4-FZD7-SEN2	7835	32174	54039	26634	45712	CXXC4-SFRP1-WNT2B	11571	19867	35998	1771	44105
BCL9-CXXC4-FZD7	46425	56003	24176	40535	3781	CXXC4-GSK3A-SFRP4	16181	45560	3757	40121	23412
CXXC4-FZD2-PPP2CA	56822	40204	3700	13007	19199	CXXC4-JUN-WNT4	8214	33327	19909	4326	55524
CXXC4-DVL2-LRP5	1462	9699	55676	56626	29198	CXXC4-WNT1-WNT3A	47935	18433	28000	8963	43231
CSNK1D-CXXC4-FRAT1	18469	1863	38915	19191	36580	CXXC4-JUN-PITX2	40461	38937	29744	13401	491
CXXC4-FGF4-NLK	2855	14468	54057	56608	16142	CXXC4-WIF1-WNT2	4105	33661	27901	37024	52946
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT3A	50619	41748	8631	29304	47291	CXXC4-GSK3A-LRP5	45263	5278	4074	9131	51672
CXXC4-FGF4-FRAT1	51420	54605	51634	34135	52133	CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1	16005	50884	46918	47316	11230
CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2	44878	33087	4409	31710	48775	CXXC4-FZD2-SEN2	55558	49222	9026	33248	8147
CXXC4-FZD2-LRP5	17355	31560	27177	3680	19413	CXXC4-FZD1-LRP5	33358	36480	7934	26180	9486
CXXC4-FZD2-GSK3B	25844	57134	25847	4025	29324	CXXC4-NKD1-SEN2	56237	29199	16253	47019	27127
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT5A	55262	11570	2649	39122	29365	CXXC4-NKD1-TLE2	22761	23290	45133	3186	46183
CXXC4-FOXN1-FBXW4	49140	19173	9034	23774	41162	CXXC4-DVL2-WNT3A	4375	4525	24217	56901	55168
CSNK1A1-CTBP2-CXXC4	46105	8098	960	7556	56799	CXXC4-GSK3A-SEN2	49417	30833	24	2223	21591
CXXC4-FOXN1-PPP2CA	32928	38757	46239	12285	33975	CXXC4-FGF4-PPP2CA	55018	25356	52250	908	48805
CXXC4-JUN-TLE1	18183	43977	27393	32258	708	CXXC4-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1	57043	48579	3331	18087	15482
CXXC4-FOXN1-WNT2	41621	52996	19908	31572	3750	CXXC4-FRAT1-KREMEN1	27974	46025	36509	52732	2302
CXXC4-FZD1-FZD7	9893	4843	22056	5572	28133	CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3	15753	14604	51126	28189	39895
CXXC4-FOXN1-LRP5	41322	33323	4244	32296	45915	CXXC4-JUN-PPP2CA	19551	7263	1665	24659	22732
CXXC4-FGF4-LRP6	10989	44203	54091	52161	54187	CXXC4-FZD7-TCF7	7167	19199	36403	32373	53081
CXXC4-FOXN1-FZD6	53265	41956	1027	35979	29580	CXXC4-FZD2-WNT2B	32870	45529	31113	9174	49764
CXXC4-FGF4-FZD8	16483	45224	48695	31746	35461	CXXC4-NLK-TCF7L1	6370	40057	51079	27610	27206
CXXC4-FZD1-WNT4	16836	16518	42917	5692	45250	CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A	32823	7902	18426	32670	44201

Table 4: Rankings of CXXC4-X-X. A list of approximately first 125 combinations with rankings below 10,000 out of 57,155. SA - SOBOL; Implementation - martinez

of CXXC4 increased the phosphorylation of GSK3 β . This indicated that CXXC4 functioned to inhibit WNT signaling by stabilizing the destruction complex of β -catenin. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of GSK3 family along with CXXC4, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CXXC4-

GSK3A-RHO, CXXC4-FZD2-GSK3B, CXXC4-GSK3A-WNT2, CXXC4-FGF4-GSK3B, CXXC4-GSK3A-SFRP4, CXXC4-GSK3A-LRP5, CXXC4-GSK3A-SEN2 and CXXC4-GSK3A-SLC9A3R1. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.3. Examining the behaviour of WNT-CXXC4-X combinations

Andersson et al. [12] show in vivo, CXXC5 expression overlapped with BMP4 adjacent to WNT3A expression in the dorsal regions of the telencephalon, including the developing choroid plexus. CXXC5 showed partial homology with IDAX (i.e CXXC4). To study whether the WNT3A response would be affected by increased levels of CXXC5 as assessed by AXIN2 expression levels, they overexpressed CXXC5 in the neural stem cells (NSCs) by nucleofection. They found that overexpression of CXXC5 resulted in a marked attenuation of the WNT3A mediated increase in AXIN2 expression levels, which suggested that high levels of CXXC5 interfered with the response to WNT3A stimulation in NSCs. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of WNT family along with CXXC4, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CXXC4-PORCN-WNT2B, CXXC4-NLK-WNT4, CXXC4-PORCN-WNT5A, CXXC4-FGF4-WNT5A, CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT3A, CXXC4-WIF1-WNT3A, CXXC4-FOSL1-WNT5A, CXXC4-NLK-WNT2B, CXXC4-FOXP1-WNT3A, CXXC4-FRAT1-WNT2, CXXC4-FOXP1-WNT5A, CXXC4-FOXP1-WNT2, CXXC4-FZD1-WNT4, CXXC4-PORCN-WNT4, CXXC4-FZD7-WNT2B, CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3A, CXXC4-DVL2-WNT2B, CXXC4-GSK3A-WNT2, CXXC4-FGF4-WNT4, CXXC4-NKD1-WNT2B, CXXC4-PORCN-WNT3, CXXC4-SFRP1-WNT2B, CXXC4-JUN-WNT4, CXXC4-WNT1-WNT3A, CXXC4-WIF1-WNT2, CXXC4-DVL2-WNT3A, CXXC4-FGF4-WNT3, CXXC4-FZD2-WNT2B and CXXC4-NLK-WNT5A. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

6.3.4. Examining the behaviour of FZD-CXXC4-X combinations

Since it is known that WNT signaling initiated with the WNT ligands binding with the FZD, it would be nice to see if combinations of CXXC4-FZD-X also get any favourable rankings. Looking at the tables above, one finds the following combinations for members of FZD family along with CXXC4, to be prominent at 3rd order level - CXXC4-FZD7-PPP2CA, CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD1, CSNK1D-CXXC4-FZD1, CXXC4-FZD2-LEF1, CXXC4-FGF4-FZD1, CXXC4-FZD7-RHO, CXXC4-FZD2-SFRP4, CXXC4-FZD1-SEN2, CXXC4-FZD2-RHO, CXXC4-FOXP1-FZD8, CXXC4-FZD7-SEN2, BCL9-CXXC4-FZD7, CXXC4-FZD2-PPP2CA, CXXC4-FZD2-LRP5, CXXC4-FZD2-GSK3B, CXXC4-FZD1-FZD7, CXXC4-FOXP1-FZD6, CXXC4-FGF4-FZD8, CXXC4-FZD1-WNT4, CXXC4-FZD7-SFRP4, CXXC4-FZD7-WNT2B, CXXC4-FRAT1-FZD8, CXXC4-DVL2-FZD1, CXXC4-FZD7-KREMEN1, CXXC4-FZD2-SEN2, CXXC4-FZD1-LRP5, CXXC4-FZD7-TCF7 and CXXC4-FZD2-WNT2B. All these combinations indicate the existence of a possible synergy when they take a higher rank in the list of combinations.

7. Conclusion

This manuscript studies the time behaviour of 3rd order combinations of CXXC4 in WNT3A stimulated HEK 293 cells. Based on the established 2nd order combinations of the CXXC4, 3rd order combinations emerge using the machine learning based search engine. These 3rd order combinations might be of interest for further wet lab investigations.

Competing interests

No competing interest is declared.

Author contributions statement

SS conceived and designed the experiments; wrote the code; performed the experiments; analyzed the data; wrote the manuscript.

Availability of code

Code for time series data available at CERN based Zenodo on <https://zenodo.org/records/14637456>.

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Supplementary

The following files (ending with .txt and can be opened in R or in simple text processing program) with these names are made available with this manuscript. For CXXC4, (1) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-linear.txt**, (2) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-rbf.txt**, (3) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-2002.txt**, and (4) **-3-odr-TP-ranking-martinez.txt**, contain rankings for 3rd order combinations across each time point for, HSIC (linear kernel), HSIC (rbf kernel), SOBOL (2002 implementation) and SOBOL (martinez implementation), respectively.

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